

DEMAX Proposal 890320: Certificate of Analysis (CoA)

Date: 10 June 2022

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Molecule(s) requested: 50g wet cell paste, containing deuterated GbpA

Molecule(s) delivered: 1 x ~240 mL of sucrose periplasmic extract fraction, 1 x ~220 mL of magnesium periplasmic fraction prepared according to protocol from M.M. Canals.

Cell type: *E. coli* strain BL21 Tuner DE3

Selection: Kanamycin

Additives: n/a

Deuterated carbon source: d8-glycerol, d-algae extract prepared in-house from *Botryococcus braunii*

Expected level of deuteration: ~95% (based on isotope content of 6 liters of recycled D2O)

Yield: 60 g of wet cell paste processed. Extracts/fractions contain GbpA (see SDS-PAGE below). Frozen fractions supplied to user.

SDS-PAGE (Biorad Mini-Protean TGX, Any kD):

Lane 1: PageRuler Prestained (Thermofisher) (5 uL)

Lane 2: GbpA – 0h (@ induction) (12 uL cells + 3 uL 5x sample buffer)

Lane 3: GbpA – sucrose fraction (12 uL sample + 3 uL 5x SB)

Lane 4: GbpA – magnesium fraction (12 uL sample + 3 uL 5x SB)

